

SIGMA: Ensuring Reliable, Secure, and Scalable Connectivity with Satellite-Terrestrial Communication System

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Abstract—The increasing reliance on terrestrial networks for telecommunications and connectivity unveils significant challenges, particularly during natural disasters or humanitarian emergencies. The SIGMA project addresses these issues by combining satellite communication (SatCom) with 5G networks to provide resilient, secure, and dependable communication services to EU and national public authorities. SIGMA utilizes a multi-band SatCom system (X-band, military Ka-band, and civilian Ka-band), 5G user equipment, and advanced traffic management tools to ensure a seamless transition between satellite and terrestrial networks. Important communication services become possible by this method even in situations where terrestrial networks become congested or unavailable. The technical architecture of SIGMA is described in the paper. It consists of high-performance Satcom-On-the-Move (SOTM) terminals, real-time encryption solutions, and a traffic management system based on SD-WAN. Field demonstrations in three EU countries, focusing on natural disaster response, large event security, and search-and-rescue operations, will validate the platform’s effectiveness.

Index Terms—SatCom-On-The-Move, 5G Networks, Satellite Communications, Emergency Response

I. BACKGROUND

Reliable communication is essential in environments where mobility and rapid response are crucial, especially for defense operations, emergency responders, and high-mobility public authorities. Conventional telecommunications, such as voice, data, video, and connectivity services provided by terrestrial networks, including 4G and 5G, struggle to maintain service continuity in remote or high-demand areas due to network congestion, spectrum availability, and inadequate coverage in remote areas. Furthermore, natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, and large-scale humanitarian crises (e.g., conflicts or refugee movements) often disrupt terrestrial infrastructure, as demonstrated by the severe flooding in western Europe

in 2021. This event caused prolonged service interruptions, necessitating weeks of emergency measures to restore mobile network services in the hardest-hit regions [1], [2].

During such disruptions, Satellite Communications (SatCom) provide essential, reliable connectivity. For example, Starlink supported communication during the 2022 Ukraine conflict, enabling critical operations when ground networks were unavailable [3]. While SatCom is indispensable in emergencies, it has notable limitations:

- Limited capacity: Certain frequencies are exclusively reserved for military use, which restricts available spectrum for commercial applications. Additionally, even within the commercial bands, reliable capacity over high-demand regions like Europe is increasingly scarce.
- Coverage gaps: Both 5G networks and geostationary satellites experience coverage gaps, with certain regions facing inconsistent or no connectivity due to infrastructure limitations or orbital constraints.
- High costs: Satellite infrastructure deployment and maintenance are expensive. The cost is around 1,000 EUR per MHz per month, with at least 10 MHz per user. Equipment for government users is limited, and SatCom networks require significant investment in ground segments, including teleports, hubs, and backhaul links.
- Security risks: Security vulnerabilities and threats associated with satellite links are significant concerns. An example of this is the hacking of the KA-SAT network ground infrastructure in February 2022, which disrupted services and exposed the vulnerabilities of satellite communication systems [4].
- Vertical integration: Industrial players now often manage all parts of the satellite ecosystem—satellite capacity, ground infrastructure, end-user terminals, and terrestrial

networks. For governmental customers, this poses a risk, as it may force them into proprietary systems that threaten their sovereignty.

- Operational complexity: Deploying, tuning, operating, and maintaining SatCom services involves significant challenges.

To address these challenges, the SIGMA project [5] (Satellite-enabled Interoperable system ensuring GOVSATCOM services' reliability, optimal traffic Management, security, and long-term Availability for EU and national public authorities) aims to provide an integrated, robust solution for reliable, secure, and scalable communication services. SIGMA will combine satellite and terrestrial networks to offer a high-bandwidth, resilient solution for emergency responders and public authorities during crises. By overcoming the limitations of both terrestrial and satellite communication systems, SIGMA ensures continuous connectivity, enhanced coverage, and a secure, cost-effective platform for critical communication needs.

The SIGMA technical solution will integrate SatCom On-The-Move (antenna and modem on vehicle) operating across three frequency bands: X-band, military Ka-band, and civil Ka-band, with 5G user equipment connected to the terrestrial networks of Mobile Network Operators (MNOs). This integration of satellite and terrestrial networks will offer a dependable, high-bandwidth solution for emergency responders, ensuring continuous communication, extended coverage, and enhanced resilience during crises [6].

By leveraging SD-WAN technology and RF-based smart decision-making, we propose an innovative architecture designed to support applications in remote or high-latency environments. This architecture enables multiple active WAN links to optimize traffic steering, meeting specific needs of applications like real-time drone video streaming during events, telemedicine, and VoIP. On one hand, the Traffic Management tool includes a module that dynamically repoints a satellite antenna between civil and military Ka-bands based on satellite signal performance. For example, if a vehicle moves out of civil Ka-band coverage, the system will detect this change and seamlessly re-point the antenna to a military Ka-band satellite, ensuring service continuity with a single antenna. On the other hand, the Traffic Management tool steers traffic based on both network and RF performance metrics, as well as application-specific requirements, across various satellite and terrestrial links. Finally, end-to-end security is provided through an encryption device that secures data transmissions across all connections.

The SIGMA solution will be tested in real-world scenarios through three government-led use cases in EU countries: flood response with Luxembourg's Fire Brigade, large event security with France's Fire Brigade, and search and rescue operations with Germany's Armed Forces at the University of Bundeswehr, Munich.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces our proposed architecture. Section III presents a

brief overview of the technical challenges and methodology. Section V concludes the work.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The end-to-end physical architecture of the SIGMA project is shown in Figure 1. The architecture features three active WAN links operating simultaneously, optimizing bandwidth usage and ensuring continuous connectivity. The system is designed to ensure uninterrupted connectivity by utilizing multiple redundant communication links (satellite and cellular), which guarantees network reliability even in case of failure or degradation of one link.

- **Satellite Antenna (Civil and Military Ka-band):** The first satellite antenna, along with its associated SatCom modem, establishes a connection via either civil Ka-band or military Ka-band satellites. The antenna's pointing is automatically controlled by the Traffic Management Tool to ensure optimal connectivity.
- **Satellite Antenna (X-band):** A second satellite antenna and SatCom modem provide communication through an X-band satellite. This link is also dynamically managed by the Traffic Management Tool to maintain service continuity.
- **Cellular 5G/4G Link:** The third active WAN link utilizes cellular 5G/4G equipment to establish a terrestrial connection when available, offering high-bandwidth and low-latency communication. The available connection type depends on the environment and cellular coverage.

The SIGMA project architecture includes the following key components:

SGoSat antenna: For robust connectivity while on the move, the high-performance Satcom-On-The-Move (SOTM) terminal, known as SGoSat [7], is deployed on the SIGMA vehicle. Unlike traditional fixed antennas, the SGoSat antenna offers precise motion tracking, compact design, and multi-band capabilities (X/commercial Ka/government Ka), making it suitable for varied environmental conditions and adaptable for different vehicles. Developed by INSTER, it operates efficiently with any modem, enhancing deployment flexibility. The SGoSat terminal by INSTER is engineered for versatility and durability, meeting challenging environmental requirements such as temperature resistance, vibration, and water protection. Its low-profile design ensures minimal impact on vehicle dynamics, while its multi-band support enables reliable satellite connectivity across geostationary networks.

SKYWAN 5G Satcom Modem: For efficient bidirectional satellite communication, the SKYWAN 5G modem [8] is employed on the SIGMA vehicle, enabling high-throughput, real-time data transmission. This modem supports both Multi-Frequency, Time Division Multiple Access (MF-TDMA) technology and the Digital Video Broadcasting by Satellite (DVB-S2) system, providing flexibility and network efficiency for varied satellite communication needs. The SKYWAN 5G modem also ensures fast communication re-acquisition in mobile scenarios (COTM) and compensates for Doppler shift,

Fig. 1. SIGMA End-to-End Physical Architecture

making it ideal for seamless connectivity during vehicle movement. Its robust performance guarantees continuous, high-speed communication across satellite links, further enhancing the system’s operational reliability.

Traffic management tool: The SIGMA vehicle’s traffic is managed by an advanced traffic management tool designed to enhance the quality of experience (QoE) for end users. This tool leverages SD-WAN technology, which has gained significant attention in recent years, especially for terrestrial environments [9], [10]. Initially developed for terrestrial networks, SD-WAN has proven to be effective in improving network performance by dynamically steering traffic based on network metrics such as latency and jitter. However, the SIGMA traffic management tool goes beyond traditional SD-WAN solutions by incorporating radio frequency (RF) metrics such as the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and the signal-to-noise ratio (C/N0) in addition to network metrics. This allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the overall connectivity status. While traditional SD-WAN mainly relies on network layer metrics, integrating RF data provides insights into the physical layer of the communication, such as signal strength, interference, and satellite link quality. This extra layer of data helps optimize traffic steering and can lead to better performance, particularly in dynamic environments where network and RF conditions can fluctuate. The traffic management tool continuously monitors both RF and network performance in real time, adjusting traffic routing based on application needs and the current link performance. This allows for optimal decision-making and ensures that critical applications receive the necessary bandwidth and priority. Additionally, it ensures service continuity by handling session failovers (i.e., handover of ongoing sessions from one active link to another active link) during link degradation or interruptions, thereby maintaining uninterrupted communication for critical applications.

Crypto device: The cryptography solution consists of an Encryptor device, which includes both software and encryption algorithms. This robust and secure solution is designed to encrypt critical information, ensuring confidentiality and integrity. In addition to data encryption, the SIGMA system implements measures to protect against potential security threats such as eavesdropping and signal jamming. Secure key management and access control mechanisms ensure that only authorized parties can access and modify critical system configurations. In large-scale deployments, a centralized key management system at the Govsatcom Operations Centre oversees the management of cryptographic keys, though this is not applicable in the demonstration phase. The architecture is designed to scale efficiently, allowing seamless integration of additional terminals or communication links as needed, making it adaptable to changing operational demands.

The SIGMA system is designed to provide reliable, secure, and flexible communication, even in dynamic and challenging environments. By combining satellite and terrestrial networks, including 5G, SIGMA guarantees continuous connectivity through advanced technologies. Its software-defined approach optimizes data flow, ensuring efficient bandwidth usage and high performance across communication links. With end-to-end encryption, SIGMA ensures the confidentiality and integrity of transmitted data, even across networks with varying latencies and data rates. Tailored to meet the needs of critical infrastructure and emergency response systems, SIGMA enhances operational effectiveness and ensures interoperability across various platforms, making it a robust and scalable solution for modern communication challenges.

III. TECHNICAL CHALLENGES AND METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 illustrates the operation of the traffic management tool, uniquely designed to operate at both the network and

Fig. 2. Operation of the traffic management tool

physical (RF) layers, making it ideal for managing hybrid network environments. This tool leverages predictive algorithms to detect link degradation and proactively reroute traffic.

A. Automatic antenna repointing between satellites

For the SGoSat antenna, which can point at different satellites, the system continuously monitors RF performance metrics to determine when to trigger antenna repointing. The tool distinguishes between progressive and sudden link degradation by periodically fetching the SNR from the active satellite modem. If the SNR drops below a predefined threshold of 5 dB and shows progressive degradation over the last 60 seconds, the system initiates automatic actions, such as switching satellite modems or adjusting configurations through the Antenna Control Unit (ACU). Progressive degradation typically arises from atmospheric conditions like rain fade, fog, or snow, or from physical obstructions such as buildings, trees, or gradually accumulating vegetation that obscure the satellite’s line of sight. However, sudden signal interruptions can also occur, for example, when a vehicle enters a tunnel or encounters a large structure that blocks the signal path entirely. In cases of sudden degradation, the system will wait for a short period to confirm that the interruption isn’t temporary (such as passing through a tunnel) before switching satellites. This approach minimizes unnecessary switching and preserves system resources for significant, sustained interruptions.

Future improvements could further enhance antenna repointing by using location-based data. For example, by considering geographic coordinates, the system could identify known tunnel locations and predict when signal loss is likely due to terrain features. Moreover, by integrating satellite coverage information, the system could assess optimal satellite choices based on the vehicle’s location and likely signal quality, leading to even smarter switching decisions.

B. RF and Network based traffic steering

The advent of Software-Defined Wide Area Networks (SD-WAN) has made advanced traffic management possible while reducing network and equipment costs. First, SD-WAN provides a centralized, programmatic structure for deploying control applications. Second, it simplifies policy management and

traffic routing, eliminating the need for manual configurations on individual devices [11].

Current SD-WAN solutions primarily target terrestrial links (e.g., MPLS, fiber) and rely on network-layer metrics like latency and jitter for traffic steering. However, this approach may be less effective for satellite links, where RF performance metrics add critical insight into link quality. Integrating RF metrics into SD-WAN-based traffic steering could improve performance in satellite-dependent environments by providing a more comprehensive view of link conditions.

The SIGMA traffic management tool leverages this combined approach to optimize the quality of experience (QoE) for end users. This tool continuously monitors both RF and network metrics, dynamically adjusting traffic steering based on application requirements and link performance. It also handles seamless session failover (handover) to maintain connectivity during link degradation or interruptions.

To manage traffic steering and handle handovers, the system utilizes data from both the network and RF layers. The traffic management tool continuously monitors link performance through periodic probes that measure latency, jitter, and packet loss at the network layer, as well as by fetching SINR data from the modem at the RF layer.

Traffic steering rules (routing rules) are defined based on traffic types and link performance. For instance, a rule might be set to route VoIP traffic, which requires low latency, over the 5G link if available. If 5G is unavailable, the Ka-band satellite link is used as the next option, followed by the X-band satellite link as a fallback. Conversely, for file uploads, which can tolerate higher latency, traffic may be directed through the Ka-band satellite link, with the X-band and 5G links as secondary options.

Link degradation is detected primarily through monitoring the SINR levels at the RF layer. When SINR progressively degrades and falls below a predefined threshold, the system automatically fails ongoing sessions over to the next preferred link, and future sessions are similarly steered to this alternative. In the Telespazio data center, traffic consolidation enables seamless transitions between links, ensuring uninterrupted sessions. Additionally, for highly critical traffic, packet duplication across multiple links can be implemented to enhance reliability.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The goal of the SIGMA project is to validate the system’s adaptability across diverse environments, use cases, applications, and traffic types, demonstrating that it can provide reliable performance regardless of geographical location or operational context. This adaptability aims to support a unified system capable of meeting the varied requirements of multiple EU organizations.

To achieve this, the SIGMA proposal emphasizes experimental validation [5]. In this way, three field demonstrations have been planned, each representing a unique use case: a natural disaster scenario, a large event security crisis, and a Search and Rescue operation, taking place in Luxembourg,

France, and Germany, respectively. In the following, we provide a summary of the planned demonstrations to be carried out.

A. Demo in Luxembourg: Crisis communications event

Luxembourg and its neighboring countries (Germany and Belgium) have recently faced significant flooding incidents, with the most devastating occurring in 2021, resulting in over 180 deaths and extensive damage to critical infrastructure [12]. In response, LuxGovSat S.A. (LGS), in collaboration with the Grand Ducal Fire and Rescue Corps (CGDIS), plans to simulate an emergency communications scenario based on a flooding or tornado event in the rural northern part of Luxembourg. This demonstration will involve forced handovers from a mobile network to two satellite communication (SatCom) networks, simulating the impact of severe weather. A seamless transition to satellite networks will ensure continuity of a video teleconference (VTC) between the CGDIS headquarters in Luxembourg City and the fire brigade in the crisis area. The resilience of X-band communication, provided by a governmental satellite, will be tested under extreme weather conditions, with communication returning to the terrestrial network once conditions stabilize.

B. Demo in France: Communications during large cultural/sporting event

Telespazio France (TPZF) conducts a second Proof of Concept to address terrestrial network outages during cultural or sporting events in Paris, where the network collapses due to excessive demand or disasters. Telespazio has partnered with Atraksis, an association founded by French Fire Brigade officers, to foster innovation for emergency services. Atraksis works with end-users (SDIS - Departmental Fire and Rescue Service), public authorities, and industry to contribute to a European ecosystem for civilian emergency response. Together, Telespazio France and Atraksis have developed a scenario involving a Parisian event where the network is severely disrupted.

Under a high-threat alert (National Security Plan, Terrorist Attack Emergency), the SDIS must monitor the crowd continuously to ensure safety. With limited staff, they use a Line-Of-Sight (LOS) Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS) with a range of several hundred meters to provide real-time video feeds to their vehicle and Command and Control center. As the crowd moves, the vehicle may need to relocate while maintaining RPAS control, all secured by the SIGMA solution via satellite.

C. Demo in Germany: Search & Rescue Operations

In the Alpine region, mountain slides are a growing challenge due to climate change, making terrestrial communication and rescue operations for missing groups extremely difficult. As part of the third Proof of Concept, ND SatCom GmbH (NDS) plans to deploy mobile terminals (Manpack, Flyaway) in the affected area to enable efficient communication during crisis management.

The demonstration in a real-world user environment will validate the feasibility of using governmental GEO satellite capacity (X band and Ka band) as a backup for civilian GEO satellite capacity (Ka band), which can in turn back up 5G terrestrial networks. This ensures secure, resilient, and straightforward communication for end users.

During the field demonstration, end users will connect via laptops or smartphones to a car equipped with a 5G-compatible terminal station and a multi-band SatCom on the Move antenna. Satellite capacity across all bands will be utilized, alongside a teleport with an Internet-connected hub. Seamless handovers between GEO satellites and terrestrial networks will be demonstrated to ensure uninterrupted communication with low latency.

The primary objective of the SIGMA project is to establish secure and mobile connectivity. To achieve this, synergies with other EU space programs, such as EGNOS and Galileo, will also be explored from a connectivity perspective.

A key anticipated outcome of SIGMA is an end-to-end solution that meets the requirements of the EUSPA GOVSATCOM community (ENTRUSTED) and other government agencies, including Frontex, particularly in crisis management scenarios. This will be achieved through collaboration with three end-users from different EU countries, as well as the definition of use cases and demonstration scenarios.

Another significant result of SIGMA is its innovative service-based business model. Instead of investing in new infrastructure, bandwidth will be offered as a service, leveraging pooled military and civilian satellite capacity to deliver cost-effective and flexible solutions.

V. CONCLUSION

The SIGMA project aims to establish a resilient, hybrid communication environment that seamlessly integrates satellite and terrestrial networks, including 5G. With an innovative approach to automated antenna management, SIGMA allows a single satellite antenna to dynamically repoint across various satellites, enhancing adaptability and efficiency. The project also introduces a unique traffic management tool that monitors both RF and network-layer metrics, optimizing traffic steering and session failover based on real-time link performance. Additionally, end-to-end encryption safeguards all communications, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality across all transmission paths. Through comprehensive field demonstrations in three EU countries, SIGMA will validate its reliability in crisis situations, offering a robust, interoperable communication solution for emergency response and critical infrastructure.

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